

**PROCESS OF REFORMS REGARDING THE DEVELOPMENT OF STATE ART
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Abstract: In this article, the process of reforms related to the development of maqam art in Uzbekistan, maqam art and its development today, issues related to its study and teaching to young performers, and useful advice in this regard are given. This article provides general information for young people interested in maqam art and enriches their imagination about maqam.

Key words: maqam, national art, music, shashmaqam, methods, prose, weight, tone

Status is the tone that has leaked from the body of our people. Therefore, it has been living for centuries. Unfortunately, in the following years, attention to this type of auspicious and magical art seemed to decrease. However, the President's decision to develop the national status art was the moment that, as the Head of State stated in the meeting with the representatives of the creative intellectuals of Uzbekistan, we will promote the status art, which is a unique heritage of our people, not only in our country, but also We should work on promoting worldwide and, if necessary, organizing status contests at the international level. Deya's remarks and the noble efforts to preserve our national heritage as the apple of an eye and convey it to young people at the initiative of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev are the great attention paid to the development of the art of national status and is finding a bright expression from care.

The decisions of November 17, 2017 "On measures to further develop the art of Uzbek national status" became an unforgettable event in the history of our art. This document aims to deeply study the Uzbek maqom art, to develop its unique performance schools and traditions at a new stage, to create and enrich its "golden fund", to increase its international prestige and to promote it widely. the verse gained importance. The endless attention paid to the development of the national status of art gives inspiration and pleasure to all artists. The Uzbek people have a huge and unique musical heritage. "Shashmaqom" and its series, which is considered as the masterpiece of Uzbek national music art, created a beautiful example of art in harmony with our classical poetry, and the people of the world look at this high music with admiration. In our country, every two years, the international music festival "Sharq taronalari", competitions and creative projects related to the promotion of this unique musical heritage have become a good tradition. The art of maqam exists in the musical heritage of most eastern nations and is the basis of national music.

Maqams are a series of musical ensembles created in a certain order, and are a unique and polished type of compositional creativity. Maqomlar is a community of folk music in a broad sense. Because in them, in particular, in Shashmaqom, a number of aspects based on the features of weight, tones, circle methods, and the rules of connecting folk songs with poetry found their full expression in the music of Uzbek and Tajik peoples. Ghiyosuddin, the author of the "Ghiyosullugat" collection, describes it as follows: "Maqom - pardai surudro goyand" - "Maqom is called the curtain of melodies and songs.

Their theoretical issues are Kindi, Farabi, Khorezmi, Ibn Sina, Urmawi, who lived and created in the 9th-15th centuries; It is explained on a deep scientific basis in the treatises of great scientists such as Shirozi, Maroghi, Jami and Husayni. Uzbek status art has a thousand-year history. The rich meaning of the words of Uzbek status has been recognized at all times. The statuses of "Shashmaqom", "Khorazm", "Fergana - Tashkent" in our country are distinguished by the unique position of the melody and the way of performance. The period, time, and social reality have had an impact on its development and refinement over the centuries. Just as every science has its own history, the stage of formation and development, the art of status has a rich history of several centuries. Maqom is a mature and distinctive genre of oral professional music, created by composers in the Middle Ages. In 2003, "Shashmaqom" was recognized by UNESCO as a "Masterpiece of Oral and Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity", which is a practical expression of the attention and recognition of maqam art. The establishment of the Uzbek national status art center in our capital and the start of its effective activity is a continuation of great events.

The art of status, which is an invaluable artistic dictionary for us, has been expressing the human spirit, its pains and dreams, and noble aspirations on high curtains for centuries and hundreds of years. Maqam brings peace and tranquility to the soul, purity and moderation to the soul. Its miraculousness is evident in the fact that even foreigners who do not understand the Uzbek language are enchanted and listen to this ancient heritage of ours. It is necessary to mobilize all our capabilities so that the melodies, spirit and philosophy of Maqam take a deep place in the hearts and minds of our young generation. Status is a priceless spiritual heritage of our people. This art has gone through a long period of development, many artists and composers contributed to its gradual development. They contain the most subtle tones of human experience. For this reason, certain preparation is necessary to feel and understand the status. For this, a person should love music from a young age, connect his spiritual maturity with this aspect. Hearing a status does not mean fully understanding it. As for the way of performance, it is a separate art, a separate culture. A common aspect in the status of the Turkic peoples is that special importance is attached to the climax and completion of the melody. The climaxes are louder, and the finale is played with a

heart-pleasing elegance.

Status is a very large category. It differs from other musical works in that it has perfect, melodic and form systems. Therefore, when performing the status, first of all, it is necessary to be familiar with classical literature. If the performer does not understand the meaning of a word while working on the status, he will not be able to sing the ghazal properly, that is, a wall will appear between the poet and the hafiz. Status is a great science. Status should be free from the pretentious words and behavior of amateur singers. Status is a rich treasure that is passed down from our ancestors to our generations. It is necessary to preserve it and to be able to deliver it without any damage to the young artists of today. And for this, first of all, we need to understand the essence of this golden art, understand and perform its magic glitters, heart-shaking veils in its original state. Otherwise, if we try to convey to the younger generation a concept that we have not fully understood, it may be our lack of education and disrespect for this masterpiece of art. It is advisable to follow the following tips when studying the art of status. - Determining the qualifications of the performer of a musical work. What does it mean? For example: for a student who is studying a work, this work is important. If it is the first work, then it is permissible to choose an easy and shorter work. Depending on the increasing skill, it is appropriate to make the works more complicated. - Determining the voice of the performer of a musical piece. In this case, it is known that the balance of the performer's voice should match the climax of the selected work.

That is, if the climax of the performer's voice is always on the "Fa" note, and the climax of the selected piece is on the "Lya" note, it will cause difficulty and inconvenience to the performer. - Determining the origin of a musical work. For example: Let's take "Adolat Tanovor". It is said that this piece of music was performed for a girl named Adolat by her brother. The origin of works such as "Munojot" shows the state of performance of the musical work by itself. So knowing the origin of a piece of music makes the circumstances of its performance more original. - Understanding the words and their meaning in a musical piece. Determining the original meaning of the words in the musical piece being performed gives a special magic and naturalness to the words during the performance.

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